

Comparative Analysis of Performance of SOFA and qSOFA Scoring System in Critically ill Patients in Emergency Department

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Abstract:

Aim: To evaluate the performance of SOFA and qSOFA scoring system at time of presentation to measure the mortality risk estimates in critically ill patients in emergency department of ACSR GMC/GGH Nellore.

Methods: All critically ill patients requiring intubation & mechanical ventilation in ED at our tertiary care teaching hospital were studied.

Results: Mean age of the present study population was 60.12±15.7 years. Mean duration of hospital stay in expired cases was 4.2 days & among survived cases was 8.95 days. The mortality rate observed in our study was 25%. The mean SOFA score was 7.1±2.7 and 4.1±1.98 in non-survived & survived cases (p<0.0001). The mean qSOFA score was 1.9±0.69 and 1.5±0.69 in non-survived & survived cases (p<0.0001). The mean duration of hospital stay was 4.2±3.9 days and 8.95±6.9 days in non-survived & survived cases. ROC-curve of SOFA shows an area of 0.85 (95% CI: 0.685-0.991; p<0.0001) with a cut-off of SOFA score >6 with a sensitivity and specificity were 87% and 62% respectively. ROC-curve of qSOFA shows an area of 0.74 (95% CI: 0.598-0.862; p<0.0001) with a cut-off of qSOFA score >2 with a sensitivity and specificity were 84% and 57% respectively. This concludes that SOFA score is the better prognostic scoring system in predicting in hospital mortality than qSOFA scoring system. The area under ROC curve of SOFA at the time of admission for predicting mortality in critically ill patients who requires intubation in emergency department was 0.85 (95% CI;0.685-0.991) is significantly higher than qSOFA with area under ROC curve 0.74(95% CI; 0.598-0.862).

Conclusion: SOFA score is the better prognostic scoring system in predicting in hospital mortality than qSOFA scoring system in patients who requires intubation.

Keywords: Critically Ill, Emergency Department, qSOFA Score.

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Introduction

Currently there is sufficient evidence substantiating the central role of the ED in the management of critically ill patients [1]. The role of the ED in stabilizing and significantly improving outcomes in critically ill patients can be emphasized. The management of the critically ill patient in the emergency department (ED) is an evolving process. Various studies show that improved outcomes in patients with severe sepsis & septic shock treated with early goal-directed therapy in the ED [2]. There are significant short- and long-term benefits in early goal-directed therapy of critically ill patients in the ED and there is a reduction of in hospital mortality [2].

There were significant short- and long-term benefits in early goal-directed therapy of critically ill patients in the ED and there was an absolute reduction of 16% in hospital mortality [3]. Although there is considerable overlap between the critical

care practiced in the ED and that practiced in an intensive care unit, significant differences still exist [4]. Emergency physicians receive patients from the community who are undifferentiated, undiagnosed, unaccessed, and unresuscitated. Most patients arrive in the intensive care unit (ICU) having undergone an initial assessment, resuscitation, and stabilization, often in the ED of same hospital or different hospital.

Additionally, there are now several time-sensitive interventions targeting critically ill patients across a spectrum of etiologies that EDs are charged with mastering and executing to improve patient outcome [2,4]. Several disease severity scoring systems have evolved for predicting the mortality in critically ill patients. SOFA (Sequential Sepsis-related organ failure assessment), qSOFA (quick sequential sepsis related organ failure assessment),

SIRS (Systemic Inflammatory response syndrome), APACHE (Acute Physiology And Chronic Health Evaluation II), LODS Logistic organ dysfunction score are some of them [5-10]. The sepsis-3 Task force itself has strongly encouraged independent validation in multiple health care setting to confirm its robustness and suggested qSOFA.

SOFA score (Sequential organ failure assessment) is based on six different scores, one each for the respiratory, cardiovascular, hepatic, coagulation, renal and neurological systems [2, 3, 4]. The SOFA score is calculated on admission and every 24 hours until discharge using the worst parameters measured during the prior 24 hours. qSOFA (quick SOFA) score is a bedside prompt that may identify patients with suspected Infection who are great risk for poor outcome outside the intensive care unit (ICU). It uses three criteria, assigning one point for low blood pressure($SBP \leq 100$ mmHg), high respiratory rate($RR \geq 22$ breaths/min), or altered mentation (Glassgow coma scale <15)[5].

qSOFA score is a bedside prompt that may identify patients with suspected infection who are at great risk for poor outcome outside the intensive care unit (ICU). It uses three criteria, assigning one point for low blood pressure($SBP \leq 100$ mmHg), high respiratory rate($RR \geq 22$ breaths/min), or altered mentation (Glassgow coma scale <15).

The current study is undertaken to evaluate the performance of SOFA and qSOFA Scoring systems in providing mortality risk estimates in critically ill patients who requires intubation in ED at time of presentation to Emergency Department.

Material and Methods

Study Type: Prospective study.

Study area: Department of Emergency medicine, ACSR GMC/GGH Nellore

Study Population: All patients presenting to emergency department requiring intubation and subsequently admitted into acute care unit.

Inclusion Criteria:

All adult patients presenting to Emergency department requiring intubation and subsequently admitted into intensive care unit, Respiratory Intensive care unit.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients relatives unwilling to participate in the study.
2. Patients surviving less than 24 hours after intubation.

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee. A written informed consent was obtained from all

the study cases. In case the patient was unconscious, consent was obtained from next responsible attendant.

Clinical evaluation: Clinical evaluation was done by taking history about present illness, past history from patient's family members. A complete history include present complaints, treatment to date, past illness and operations, current medications and any known allergies were documented. Initial assessment of the patient's Airway, Breathing, Circulation and level of consciousness were noted and documented. As treatment proceeds a secondary and more detailed survey was conducted to refine the preliminary diagnosis and assess the response to initial treatment.

Laboratory variables: Standard biochemistry, hematology, microbiology and radiologic tests were performed. The single most useful test in an acutely ill patient is an arterial blood gas analysis. From the above laboratory data and clinical evaluation, base line SOFA and qSOFA score were calculated at the time of admission.

Outcome: To assess performance of SOFA & qSOFA scoring systems in providing risk estimates in critically ill patients presenting to Emergency medicine department, ACSR GMC/GGH Nellore.

Statistical analysis: Data recorded in a predesigned proforma and statistical analysis done using statistical software IBM SPSS statistics version 22.0. Receiver operator characteristic curve (ROC curve) was plotted for SOFA & qSOFA score for the prediction of hospital mortality. The area under ROC curve (AUC) was considered a composite index of discrimination. The performance of SOFA & qSOFA were compared by comparing the AUC.

Results

The mean age of patients was 61.5 ± 15.5 years. Majority cases were belongs to 7th & 8th decade. 65% were males and 35% were females. The commonest indications for intubation and mechanical ventilation was acute pulmonary edema (12%), Acute respiratory distress syndrome(8%), pneumonia(20%), COPD and carbondioxide narcosis(10%), severe metabolic acidosis(9%), poor GCS & aspiration(15%), Refractory Shock(8%), and multiple causes(18%). In our study, 10% patients had meningitis, 28% patients were diagnosed as lower respiratory tract infection, 16% patients admitted with septicemia, bowel pathology including intestinal obstruction and perforation in 4%, UTI(17%), postpartum sepsis (3%), soft tissue cellulitis in 9%.

Table 1: Basic parameters recorded at admission

	Result	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
SOFA	non-survived	75	7.1	2.7	<0.0001
	survived	25	4.1	1.98	
qSOFA	non-survived	75	1.9	0.69	<0.0001
	survived	25	1.5	0.69	
Duration of Hospital Stay	non-survived	75	4.2	3.9	<0.0001
	survived	25	8.95	6.9	

The mean SOFA score was 7.1 ± 2.7 and 4.1 ± 1.98 in non-survived & survived cases ($p < 0.0001$). The mean qSOFA score was 1.9 ± 0.69 and 1.5 ± 0.69 in non-survived & survived cases ($p < 0.0001$). The mean duration of hospital stay was 4.2 ± 3.9 days and 8.95 ± 6.9 days in non-survived & survived cases.

Predictors for Mortality in hospital:

Calculation of cut-off values of SOFA score for prediction of mortality.

Median value of SOFA Score among the study population was 6.

Table 2: Outcome measurement by SOFA and qSOFA score system.

		SOFA				Total		P Value
		+ Ve		- Ve				
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
SOFA	non-survived	48	48	27	27	75	75.0	<0.0001
	survived	4	4	21	21	25	25.0	
		qSOFA						<0.0001
qSOFA	non-survived	46	46	29	29.0	75	75.0	
	survived	3	3	22	22.0	25	25.0	

At a cut off value of 6 of sofa score, percentage of sofa score with true positive value is 45%, false positive 20%, false negative 8% and true negative is 32%. Sensitivity of SOFA score is 87% and specificity is 62%.

At a cut off value of 2 of qsofa score, the percentage of qsofa score with true positive value is 44%, false positive 21%, false negative 7% and true negative is 29%. Sensitivity of SOFA score is 84% and specificity is 57%

Table 3: ROC analysis of SOFA, and qSOFA

	AUC	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
SOFA	0.85	0.042	<0.0001	0.685	0.991
qSOFA	0.74	0.039	<0.0001	0.598	0.862

Discussion

Mean age of the present study population was 60.12 ± 15.7 years. Study results comparable in a study by Muhammad Akbar Baig et al, [11] in which the mean age was 59.6 ± 17.2 years. Males outnumbered than females in our present study. This observation was similar to the finding in a study by Acharya SP [12].

Respiratory failure is the most common cause for intubation in ED this is comparable with the study done by M.H.Rao et al [13]. Mean duration of hospital stay in expired cases was 4.2 days & among survived cases was 8.95 days. Patients who survived stayed for longer duration in hospital compared to non-survivors, our results are in consistent with study by M.H.Rao et al. The mortality depends upon many factors like etiological cause, availability of first aid services nearby, time lapse between onset of symptoms and

presentation to hospital, availability of technical expertise in handling these emergencies. The mortality rate observed in our study was 25%. Whereas the mortality was 54% is reported by Madhan et al [14], in which they evaluated value of SOFA scores in predicting prognosis in patients with VAP. In a study from Pietraszek-Grzywaczewska I et al [15] overall in hospital mortality was between 15-40%. The mortality rate observed in our study may be due to referral bias as the sickest patients being referred to the tertiary care hospital.

Factors associated with mortality included higher age, higher SOFA & qSOFA score were found in those patients who died compared with survived cases. The mean SOFA score was 7.1 ± 2.7 and 4.1 ± 1.98 in non-survived & survived cases ($p < 0.0001$).

The mean qSOFA score was 1.9 ± 0.69 and 1.5 ± 0.69 in non-survived & survived cases ($p < 0.0001$). The mean duration of hospital stay was 4.2 ± 3.9 days and 8.95 ± 6.9 days in non-survived & survived cases. Calculation of cut-off values of SOFA score for prediction of mortality. Median value of SOFA Score among the study population was 6. At a cut off value of 6 of sofa score, percentage of sofa score with true positive value is 45%, false positive 20%, false negative 8% and true negative is 32%. Sensitivity of SOFA score is 87% and specificity is 62%. At a cut off value of 2 of qsofa score, the percentage of qsofa score with true positive value is 44%, false positive 21%, false negative 7% and true negative is 29%. Sensitivity of SOFA score is 84% and specificity is 57%.

ROC-curve of SOFA shows an area of 0.85 (95% CI: 0.685-0.991; $p < 0.0001$) with a cut-off of SOFA score > 6 with a sensitivity and specificity were 87% and 62% respectively. ROC-curve of qSOFA shows an area of 0.74 (95% CI: 0.598-0.862; $p < 0.0001$) with a cut-off of qSOFA score > 2 with a sensitivity and specificity were 84% and 57% respectively. This concludes that SOFA score is the better prognostic scoring system in predicting in hospital mortality than qSOFA scoring system.

A study from Jones E A et al [16] reported that non survivors had significantly higher mean SOFA score of 9.8 points compared to survivors with a mean value of 6.5 which is similar to present study. In our study at a median cut-off value of SOFA score > 6 the sensitivity and specificity were 88.1% and 61.5% respectively. The area under ROC-curve along with 95 % confidence bounds=0.841, standard error =0.040, this is comparable with study in Khwannimit B et al [17] area under ROC curve for SOFA score is 0.839 in predicting mortality in sepsis patients admitted to ICU. Crude area under ROC was 0.753 in predicting mortality. Khwannimit B et al area under ROC for qSOFA (AUC 0.814, $P = 0.003$) and also comparable with Lucie probst et al [18].

Area under ROC for qSOFA in predicting mortality in haematological cancer patients was 0.65(95% CI, 0.60-0.71). The present study therefore provides valuable data in assessing the clinical manifestations and outcome in patients presenting with critical illness to emergency department admitted to ICU.

Conclusion

The mean duration of hospital stay in days was significantly higher in alive when compared to death patients. The area under ROC curve of SOFA at the time of admission for predicting mortality in critically ill patients who requires intubation in emergency department was 0.85 (95% CI;0.685-0.991) is significantly higher than qSOFA with area under ROC curve 0.74(95% CI; 0.598-0.862)

which indicates SOFA is the better performer in predicting mortality when compared to qSOFA.

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